

Synthesis and hydrogen storage performance of Al₂O₃ nanoparticle decorated functionalized multi-walled carbon nanotubes (Al₂O₃@f-MWCNTs)

Madhavi Konni and Saratchandra Babu Mukkamala*

Nanoscience & Nanotechnology Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, Institute of Science, GITAM (Deemed University), Visakhapatnam-530 045, Andhra Pradesh, India

E-mail: mscbabu@gmail.com

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Al₂O₃ nanoparticle decorated functionalized Multi-Walled Carbon Nanotubes (Al₂O₃@f-MWCNTs) have been synthesized to examine the hydrogen storage performance at non-cryogenic temperatures and moderate pressures for green energy applications. The experimental conditions such as solvent medium and metal content have been tuned to improve the decoration of Al₂O₃ nanoparticles on the surface of carboxylate-functionalized multi-walled carbon nanotubes (COOH-MWCNTs/f-MWCNTs). The morphology, surface properties and structure of compounds were characterized by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM), FT-IR and powder X-ray diffraction. The hydrogen uptake of materials was examined by High Pressure Gas Adsorption System at non-cryogenic temperatures i.e. 253 K and 298 K up to 70 bar pressure. Al₂O₃@f-MWCNTs prepared in water, triethylamine and DMF adsorbed 0.46, 0.55 and 0.67 wt% of hydrogen at 253 K and 0.17, 0.31 and 0.46 wt% of hydrogen at 298 K, respectively. The higher uptake of hydrogen by Al₂O₃@f-MWCNTs prepared in DMF is due to uniform loading of metal nanoparticles on the surface of carbon nanotubes.

Keywords: Functionalization, P-MWCNTs, f-MWCNTs, Al₂O₃ nanoparticles, hydrogen storage.

Introduction

Hydrogen is considered as a future fuel due to its high energy content (143 MJ/Kg) and eco-friendly characteristics. Storage of hydrogen is a key enabling technology for onboard vehicle applications. Physical techniques such as high pressure and cryogenic storage methods are not ideal for transport applications, due to the risk associated with them¹⁻³. Extensive research has been focused on the development of solid-state storage medium for hydrogen over the last few decades but none of them matched with the targets set by U.S. Department of Energy (DOE) (7.5 wt% at non-cryogenic conditions)⁴⁻⁶. Carbon-based materials such as graphene, carbon nanotubes and C₆₀ are considered to be promising a hydrogen storage medium because of their lightweight, pore structure and high surface area⁷⁻¹². However, at room temperature, due to weak van der Waals interaction and low binding energy (0.11 eV), pristine carbon nanostructures exhibit poor hydrogen uptake¹³⁻¹⁵. But the binding energy of 0.20–0.60 eV is necessary for sufficient hydrogen uptake to meet the DOE target for onboard transport applications¹⁶⁻¹⁸. Hydrogen uptake capacity can be enhanced by increasing

the binding energy of carbon nanostructures through decorating with alkali (Li, Na and K)^{19,20}, alkaline earth (Be, Mg and Ca)^{7,21-23}, transition metals (Sc, Ti, V, Pd and Pt)²⁴⁻²⁶, and metal hydrides²⁷⁻²⁹.

Alumina (Al₂O₃) is thermodynamically stable crystalline material and commonly using as ceramic composite³⁰, cements and liners³¹, synthetic biomaterial³². Recent reports show that Al-modified graphene is recommended for hydrogen storage as well as gas sensor applications. Ao *et al.*^{33,34} reported that Al-doped graphene can store H₂ molecules up to 5.13 wt% at 300 K and 0.1 GPa. The adsorption binding energy observed in this case is 0.260 eV/H₂. Further, as reported by Ao and Peeters³⁵, Al loaded graphene could adsorb 13.79 wt% of hydrogen at an average binding energy of 0.193 eV/H₂ calculated through DFT. Carrete *et al.* predicted through DFT calculations that Al decorated graphene nanoribbons (GNRs) can adsorb a sufficient amount of hydrogen to meet the DOE targets. Another recent theoretical study shows that Al-decorated porous graphene adsorbs 10.5 wt% of hydrogen with an enhanced binding energy of 0.41 eV/H₂³⁶. So, to the best of our knowledge, there are very

few reports on the experimental investigation of hydrogen storage behaviour of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{MWCNTs}$ nanoparticles. In this paper, the influence of different solvents such as water, amine and DMF on the decoration of nanoparticles on surface f-MWCNTs and hydrogen storage performance at non-cryogenic temperatures and moderate pressures are presented.

Experimental

Materials:

$\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and triethylamine purchased from Merck, India and dimethylformamide (DMF) was procured from Fisher Scientific.

Functionalization of MWCNTs:

0.3 g of purified multi-walled carbon nanotubes (p-MWCNTs) and 150 ml nitration mixture (1:3 HNO_3 and H_2SO_4) were refluxed for 48 h under magnetic stirring. The obtained functionalized MWCNTs (COOH-MWCNTs/f-MWCNTs) were washed with the deionized water and dried overnight in vacuum at 40°C .

Preparation of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3@f\text{-MWCNTs}$:

200 mg of carboxylate functionalized MWCNTs (f-MWCNTs) and 7.50 g [0.02 mol, High metal concentration (HMC)] or 3.75 g [0.01 mol, Low metal concentrations (LMC)] of $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ were taken in a 500 ml round bottomed flask. To this, 150 ml distilled water/150 ml distilled water containing 0.5 ml triethylamine (TEA)/150 ml dimethylformamide (DMF) was mixed thoroughly and heated at 80°C for 6 h (solution pH of the aqueous medium was ~ 7.0 and TEA medium was ~ 10.0). The resulting solid was washed till the pH of washing was neutral. The sample was dried overnight in vacuum at 40°C .

Characterization methods:

FEI Quanta 200 FEG Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) and Philips CM 200 Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM) are used to examine the morphology/texture of synthesized compounds. The FT-IR spectra of samples were measured using Perkin-Elmer Spectrum two spectrophotometer. Diffraction patterns were recorded with the help of PANalytical X'Pert PRO powder X-ray diffractometer with graphite monochromatic $\text{CuK}\alpha$ ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$) radiation. The BET surface area was determined using Quantachrome NOVA 1200e. High-pressure gas adsorption system (BELSORP-HP) is used for hydrogen gas sorption measurements.

Results and discussion

The surface morphology of Al_2O_3 nanoparticle decorated MWCNTs was examined by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) and Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM). Fig. 1 shows the SEM image of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3@f\text{-MWCNTs}$. The surface of MWCNTs displays that carbon nanotube measures about 20–40 nm diameter with few micrometres length. The presence

Fig. 1. (a) SEM image of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3@f\text{-MWCNTs}$ and (b) SEM image of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3@f\text{-MWCNTs}$ with elemental mapping.

of MWCNTs along with Al_2O_3 nanoparticles is confirmed from this SEM image together with the corresponding elemental mapping. The EDAX measurements (Fig. 2) show the composition of carbon, oxygen, aluminium from $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3@f\text{-MWCNTs}$. The TEM images (Fig. 3) reveals that Al_2O_3 nanoparticles were successfully loaded on the surface of CNTs. It was seen from the TEM images (Fig. 3a) that in $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3@f\text{-MWCNTs}$, the spherical alumina (Al_2O_3) nanoparticles were found to be uniformly distributed covering a large area of the nanotube network. The size of the metal oxide nanoparticles varied from 5 to 20 nm.

Fig. 2. EDAX image of Al₂O₃@f-MWCNTs.

tion of pores of the p-MWCNTs by COOH functional groups after surface functionalization. The surface area is further reduced from 236 m²/g to 206, 194 and 23 m²/g for Al₂O₃@f-MWCNTs prepared in water, amine and DMF, respectively. This decrease in surface area is due to blocking of some more pores by Al₂O₃ nanoparticles.

The hydrogen adsorption capacities of Al₂O₃ decorated MWCNTs along with pristine and functionalized MWCNTs were measured volumetrically at 253 K and 298 K at moder-

Fig. 3. (a) TEM image of Al₂O₃@f-MWCNTs and (b) magnified TEM image of Al₂O₃@f-MWCNTs.

The FT-IR spectra of pristine-MWCNTs, f-MWCNTs, and Al₂O₃@f-MWCNTs are shown in Fig. 4. The two peaks at 2920 cm⁻¹ and 2854 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the C-H stretching vibrations. The adsorption peak at 1682 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the stretching vibration of C=O from -COOH. This indicates the formation of functionalized MWCNTs (COOH-MWCNTs/f-MWCNTs) (Fig. 4a and 4b). The peak at 655 cm⁻¹ corresponds to the Al-O bond.

Fig. 5 shows the powder X-ray diffraction patterns of the pristine MWCNTs and Al₂O₃@f-MWCNTs. The diffraction pattern shows broad 2 theta peaks around 25.4° and 42.9° corresponding to the (101) and (100) reflections of CNTs, respectively. The diffraction peaks (Fig. 5b) at 19.2°, 20.1°, 37.4° and 39.9° correspond to (111), (012), (110) and (113) planes of Al₂O₃ nanoparticles, respectively.

The BET specific surface area of p-MWCNTs, f-MWCNTs and Al₂O₃@f-MWCNTs determined by N₂ absorption measurements at 77 K are shown in Table 1. The surface area of p-MWCNTs and f-MWCNTs is 360 m²/g and 236 m²/g, respectively. This decrease in surface area is due to occupa-

Fig. 4. FT-IR spectra of (a) Al₂O₃@f-MWCNTs, (b) f-MWCNTs and (c) p-MWCNTs.

ate pressures i.e. up to 70 bar using high-pressure gas sorption analyser, BELSORP-HP. Adsorption of hydrogen on MWCNTs and Al₂O₃@f-MWCNTs is reversible (Fig. 6), so desorption curves are omitted in all hydrogen uptake illustrations for clarity. It was observed that the hydrogen adsorption capacity of pristine and f-MWCNTs at 253 K and 70

Fig. 5. Powder XRD patterns of (a) p-MWCNTs and (b) Al₂O₃@f-MWCNTs.

Table 1. BET surface area and hydrogen uptake capacity of Al₂O₃@f-MWCNTs

Sample	Reaction medium	^s BET (m ² /g)	H ₂ uptake at 253 K and 70 bar (wt%)	H ₂ uptake at 298 K and 70 bar (wt%)
p-MWCNTs	–	360	0.30	0.12
f-MWCNTs	–	236	0.09	0.06
Al ₂ O ₃ @f-MWCNTs	Water	206	0.31 ^a 0.46 ^b	0.13 ^a 0.17 ^b
Al ₂ O ₃ @f-MWCNTs	Triethyl-amine	194	0.42 ^a 0.55 ^b	0.22 ^a 0.31 ^b
Al ₂ O ₃ @f-MWCNTs	DMF	23	0.46 ^a 0.67 ^b	0.31 ^a 0.46 ^b

^aLMC – Low metal concentration. ^bHMC – High metal concentration.

bar pressure was 0.31 and 0.09 wt%, respectively. At 298 K the hydrogen adsorption capacity of pristine and COOH-MWCNTs was 0.12 and 0.06 wt%, respectively. So, it was observed that at low temperatures material exhibited high uptake capacity compared to room temperatures. Al₂O₃@f-MWCNTs prepared at LMC in water, triethylamine and DMF adsorb 0.31, 0.42 and 0.46 wt% of hydrogen (Fig. 7) whereas Al₂O₃@f-MWCNTs prepared at HMC adsorbs 0.46, 0.55 and 0.67 wt% (Fig. 8), respectively at 253 K. This result indicates that the hydrogen sorption property drastically increases on increasing the Al₂O₃ nanoparticle content on surface of f-MWCNTs. Fig. 9 shows that the hydrogen adsorption iso-

Fig. 6. Hydrogen sorption by Al₂O₃@f-MWCNTs in TEA at 298 K at HMC: (a) desorption and (b) adsorption.

Fig. 7. Hydrogen storage by MWCNTs at 253 K at LMC: (a) Al₂O₃@f-MWCNTs in DMF, (b) p-MWCNTs, (c) Al₂O₃@f-MWCNTs in TEA, (d) Al₂O₃@f-MWCNTs in H₂O and (e) COOH-MWCNTs.

Fig. 8. Hydrogen storage by MWCNTs at 253 K at HMC: (a) Al₂O₃@f-MWCNTs in DMF, (b) p-MWCNTs, (c) Al₂O₃@f-MWCNTs in TEA, (d) Al₂O₃@f-MWCNTs in H₂O and (e) COOH-MWCNTs.

Fig. 9. Hydrogen storage by MWCNTs at 298 K at LMC: (a) Al₂O₃@f-MWCNTs in DMF, (b) p-MWCNTs, (c) Al₂O₃@f-MWCNTs in TEA, (d) Al₂O₃@f-MWCNTs in H₂O and (e) COOH-MWCNTs.

therms recorded at 298 K for Al₂O₃@f-MWCNTs prepared at LMC in water, triethylamine and DMF indicated 0.13, 0.22 and 0.31 wt% of adsorption. Similarly, Al₂O₃@f-MWCNTs prepared at HMC under the aforementioned reaction conditions adsorbed 0.17, 0.31 and 0.46 wt% of hydrogen (Fig. 10). The data on the hydrogen storage capacity of Al₂O₃@f-MWCNTs is presented in Table 1. The higher uptake observed by Al₂O₃@f-MWCNTs is due to spillover effect (dissociation of molecular hydrogen by Al₂O₃ and transported as atomic hydrogen to the surface of MWCNTs).

Fig. 10. Hydrogen storage by MWCNTs at 298 K at HMC: (a) Al₂O₃@f-MWCNTs in DMF, (b) p-MWCNTs, (c) Al₂O₃@f-MWCNTs in TEA, (d) Al₂O₃@f-MWCNTs in H₂O and (e) COOH-MWCNTs.

Conclusions

In this paper, the hydrogen storage performance of Al₂O₃ nanoparticle decorated f-MWCNTs examined at non-cryo-

genic conditions is presented. The hydrogen storage capacity of Al₂O₃@f-MWCNTs was 0.67 and 0.46 wt% at 253 and 298 K, respectively, which exhibited 2–3 times higher than the pristine-MWCNTs. Solvent and metal content play a key role in the decoration of Al₂O₃ on the surface of MWCNTs as well as on hydrogen storage performance.

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